

Non Intrusive Optical Performance Monitoring in Fiber Optic Networks Using Coherent Receivers as Spectrum Analyzers

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ABSTRACT Optical networks of the future are expected to address different user needs, adapting to specific requirements and the overall condition of the network. Achieving this flexibility necessitates a profound understanding of the network, attainable only by means of optical performance monitoring techniques. This paper deals with the utilization of common coherent transceivers for spectrum analysis, transforming them into non-intrusive optical probes irrespective of the modulation format. We aim to showcase the functionality of these probes, exploring and evaluating their performance while reviewing their limits.

Keywords Optical performance monitoring, coherent receivers, optical networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Proactive and reactive automation of optical networks is arguably the most significant challenge that needs to be addressed in order to further increase efficiency and cost-effectiveness of telecommunication networks. Such automation is based on actively processing network monitoring information and learning from the effects of the decisions taken to validate and provide optimal selection of network resources to satisfy the different service demands and dynamically re-optimize them. So, the key elements of a transport network are the optical performance monitoring systems that are expected to deliver the feedback needed for guaranteeing end-to-end quality of transmission (QoT) and quality of service (QoS). In fact, the monitoring of the communication infrastructure is crucial for achieving an efficient network operation and management, allowing to reduce or even discard safety margins without risking performance and/or resource utilisation inefficiencies.

Several techniques can be employed for acquiring, processing and estimating the different physical and transmission parameters needed for performance monitoring. In the available literature we can find approaches that range from highly intrusive receiver-based monitoring [1] to non-intrusive optical probes independent from the modulation format [2].

Intrusive techniques are usually utilizing one or more optical paths only for monitoring purposes. They are based on demodulating and equalizing signals to obtain the desired performance metrics and typically acquire the performance in a channel by channel and/or path by path basis. Among the different available options, a convenient one is based on coherent reception [1]. This option can provide many interesting figures of merit, including bit error ratio (BER) prior to error correction, optical signal to noise ratio (OSNR), Q-factor, wavelength, power, chromatic dispersion, and relative state of polarization [1]. Therefore, they can provide detailed information of a given lightpath at the expense of occupying the associated resources (e.g. spectral slots). Nevertheless, they fail to provide a network-wide diagnostic. In order to solve this issue, it is desirable to deploy a non-intrusive optical performance monitoring system at the network nodes to automatically extract the different performance parameters [3].

In this paper we advance the network monitoring probes discussed in [3], which are based on optical spectrum analysis. Their modular approach comes with different options for optoelectronic front-ends and digital signal processing (DSP) modules [3], [4], allowing the measurements to be enhanced by using artificial intelligence [2]. Precisely, here we aim to evaluate the reuse of spare/unused coherent transceivers for such non-intrusive spectrum measurements. The reason behind is that nowadays aggregation and transport optical networks are mostly based on transceivers featuring coherent reception, able to detect polarization multiplexed signals featuring QAM constellations with symbol rates exceeding 25 Gbaud [5]. Although being pluggable and easily exchangeable/replaceable, each of these transceivers comes at a non-negligible cost, as it may exceed several tens of thousands of euro. So, we aim to explore an additional use for them in order to enhance the return on investment when incorporating them in a given network.

2. CONCEPT

The main concept is shown in figure 1. There, a sample route-and-select node is depicted, that includes optical wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and demultiplexing stages and a switching backplane. Next to the optical amplifier attached to the optical multiplexing stage, there is a signal tap: which consists of an N:M

Figure 1. (a) Sample route-and-select node including a signal tap properly wired for the performance monitoring approach. (b) Generic optical spectrum of a signal under test.

Figure 2. Typical scheme of a coherent receiver featuring phase and polarization diversities.

optical coupler that is used for delivering back to the node a copy of the transmitted signal. In order to limit the insertion loss, a 90:10 or 99:1 coupler can be used, featuring losses below 1 dB. The output port of the signal tap is directly attached to the switching backplane, so that it can be connected to any of the transceivers (TRXs) attached to the node. Interestingly, it can be connected to a spare/unused coherent optical transceiver, e.g. for redundancy purposes.

This spare transceiver is used for estimating the optical spectrum of the signal fed by the tap. Unfortunately, coherent optical transceiver modules can not be continuously swept across the optical spectrum as in typical coherent optical spectrum analyzers [6], but they only can be tuned in steps according to the ITU-T flexible grid [?]. This limits the frequency to be defined in steps of 6.25 GHz. So, we propose to use the spare transceivers to detect and compute different spectral slices of the signals under test, reconstructing the entire spectra by putting together the spectrum of each slice.

A sample implementation of a typical coherent receiver scheme is shown in figure 2. There, the received slice of signal under test $E_r(t)$ and the local laser signal $E_l(t)$, first pass through a polarization beam splitter (PBS) stage, that decompose them into the two orthogonal H and V states. Next, each optical signal H and V pair is combined in a 90 degree optical hybrid and the corresponding balanced detection stages for obtaining a phase diversity reception. In other words, let's assume that $E_r(t)$ can be expressed using the Jones formalism

$$E_r(t) = \begin{bmatrix} E_{Hr}(t) \\ E_{Vr}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_{Hr}(t) \\ e_{Vr}(t) \end{bmatrix} \exp(j2\pi f_s t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{P_r(t)}{2}} \cos(\varphi_r) \exp(j\phi_{rH}(t)) \\ \sqrt{\frac{P_r(t)}{2}} \sin(\varphi_r) \exp(j\phi_{rV}(t) + j\theta_r) \end{bmatrix} \exp(j2\pi f_s t) \quad (1)$$

where $P_r(t)$ is the optical power, φ_r is the azimuth of the state of polarization (SOP), being f_s the central frequency of the slice; $\phi_{rH}(t)$ and $\phi_{rV}(t)$ are the phases of the H and V components of the signal; and θ_r is the azimuth of the SOP.

The signal coming from the local laser can be also expressed in similar terms

$$E_l(t) = \begin{bmatrix} E_{Hl}(t) \\ E_{Vl}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_{Hl}(t) \\ e_{Vl}(t) \end{bmatrix} \exp(j2\pi f_s t) \quad (2)$$

This laser is a continuous wave laser that is usually integrated together with the receiver and its SOP is aligned with the PBS according to a $+45^\circ$ linear polarization. In that case

$$e_{Hl}(t) = e_{Vl}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{P_l}{2}} \exp(j\phi_l(t)) \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_l(t)$ is the phase, mainly contributed by the phase noise of the laser.

So, after the two phase diversity detection stages, we obtain the following set of currents

$$\begin{aligned} I_{HI}(t) &= R\sqrt{\frac{P_l P_r(t)}{4}} \cos(\varphi_r) \cos(\phi_{rH}(t) - \phi_l(t)) & I_{VI}(t) &= R\sqrt{\frac{P_l P_r(t)}{4}} \sin(\varphi_r) \cos(\phi_{rV}(t) - \phi_l(t) + \theta_r) \\ I_{HQ}(t) &= R\sqrt{\frac{P_l P_r(t)}{4}} \cos(\varphi_r) \sin(\phi_{rH}(t) - \phi_l(t)) & I_{VQ}(t) &= R\sqrt{\frac{P_l P_r(t)}{4}} \sin(\varphi_r) \sin(\phi_{rV}(t) - \phi_l(t) + \theta_r) \end{aligned}$$

being R the responsivity of the photodiodes.

This way, after eventual digitization (not show in Figure 2), we can reconstruct the optical signal at the input as

$$S_H(n) = I_{HI}(nT) + jI_{HQ}(nT) = R \cdot e_{Hr}(nT) \cdot \bar{e}_{Hl}(nT) \quad (4)$$

$$S_V(n) = I_{VI}(nT) + jI_{VQ}(nT) = R \cdot e_{Vr}(nT) \cdot \bar{e}_{Vl}(nT) \quad (5)$$

where T is the sampling period and $\bar{e}_{Hl}(t)$ and $\bar{e}_{Vl}(t)$ are the complex conjugates of $e_{Hl}(t)$ and $e_{Vl}(t)$.

So, using the local laser (oscillating at a frequency f_s), we tune the coherent detector to a given frequency in order to detect a single slice of the signal under test. At each slice, we are able to detect the signal that lies within the range $f_s \pm B_p$, being B_p the bandwidth of the photodiodes of the coherent receiver. By processing $S_H(n)$ and $S_V(n)$, we can estimate the spectrum of each slice. For example, we can take the N -point discrete Fourier transform of those signals to obtain the corresponding spectrum

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}\{S_H(n)\} &= R\mathcal{F}\{e_{Hr}(nT)\} * \mathcal{F}\{\bar{e}_{Hl}(nT)\} \simeq R\sqrt{\frac{P_l}{2}} \mathcal{F}\{e_{Hr}(nT)\} \\ \mathcal{F}\{S_V(n)\} &= R\mathcal{F}\{e_{Vr}(nT)\} * \mathcal{F}\{\bar{e}_{Vl}(nT)\} \simeq R\sqrt{\frac{P_l}{2}} \mathcal{F}\{e_{Vr}(nT)\} \end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{F} is the discrete Fourier transform and $*$ is the convolution operator. Please, note that the local laser is intended to be continuous laser with narrow spectral width. $\mathcal{F}\{\bar{e}_{Hl}(nT)\}$ and $\mathcal{F}\{\bar{e}_{Vl}(nT)\}$ are assumed to be approximable by the dirac delta function in case $1/NT$ is much greater than the linewidth of the local laser. For example, in case of having a 150 kHz linewidth, $1/NT$ should be at least one order of magnitude higher than that (1.5 MHz). With this approximation we ensure an easy and straightforward approximation valid only for computing the power spectrum.

With this procedure we can fairly estimate the polarization-resolved optical power spectrum of each slice. Note that we foresee to acquire different slices with Δf spacing, that is intended to be smaller than B_p . The parts of each slice that are being overlapped one to each other are averaged to ensure a smooth and continuous optical spectrum.

3. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

In order to derive a first set of specifications while assessing the viability of the OPM concept, we have carried out a comparison between our solution and a commercial solution for spectrum monitoring [7].

For that, we built up a model for simulations in Python to extract preliminary results. The simulations have been carried out using the fiber optic communication simulation (FOCS) platform of CTTC, which is based on common device models fine tuned according to experimental results. Therefore, the developments and results obtained there are easily exportable and comparable to an experimental setup.

For the simulation setup, we used a model based on the datasheet of a commercial coherent receiver [8] and with a local laser featuring a transmission power of 16 dBm and linewidth of 150 kHz. First, we characterized the basic ability of the system to measure power in a relatively small frequency resolution. For that, we carried out 100 measurements per simulation with frequency resolution of 195 MHz. This resolution is set by the size of the FFT performed after coherent reception of a slice of optical spectra. Therefore, it is arbitrarily adjustable, although it should be kept well above the linewidth of the local laser as discussed in the previous section.

TABLE I
RESULTS AND COMPARISON TO COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE OPTICAL CHANNEL MONITORS.

	Approached OPM	Commercial channel monitor
Resolution	Limited by FFT size	312.5 MHz
Min. power	-22 dBm	below -50 dBm
Max. power	14 dBm	10 dBm
Polarization-resolved spectrum	Yes	No

Results of the power measurements show a dynamic range of more than 36 dB, covering from -22 dBm up to 14 dBm, while featuring a standard deviation below 0.6 dB.

Next, we made a first characterization of OSNR by feeding the system with a standard 10 Gb/s OOK IM-DD signal featuring 0 dBm of overall power. Optical white Gaussian noise was added to this signal in a controlled way, so that we can have a correspondence between OSNR of signal and measured OSNR by the reuse coherent receivers of the nodes. Results show that our approach can measure OSNRs up to 25 dB. Nevertheless, the linear correspondence between input and estimated OSNRs is up to around 15 dB, where we observe the 1 dB compression point of the measurements. Beyond that value, the OSNR estimation degrades rapidly, achieving 3dB compression at around 18 dB. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the measurements is quite high, featuring less than 0.8 dB of standard deviation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has described how conventional coherent transceivers can be used for spectrum analysis, repurposing them into non-intrusive optical probes. A preliminary performance assessment has been carried out by means of simulations, showing a dynamic range of more than 36 dB and the ability to extract OSNR values of up to 15 dB.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Work funded by the EU FLEXSCALE project (101096909), ES RELAMPAGO (PID2021-127916OB-I00) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, UE and 6G OPTRAN STERIOD (TSI-063000-2021-115) this last project funded by "Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital" and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the "Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia" and of the "Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia".

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